

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Sustainable business model tailored on touristic sector to maximise tourists' attractiveness

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

DELIVERABLE TOEP 3.3

RESEARCH MODULE 3: Sustainable practices in Tourism Destinations: tourist analysis and performance strategies

S.0.3: to investigate the impact of Sustainable practices in the tourism-hotel sector on business performance and tourists' attractiveness.

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Glossary

Definition	
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

1.1 Environmental Management Practices (EMPs) in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry

The issue of environmental sustainability is particularly relevant for businesses in the tourism and hospitality sector, both for the success and growth of companies engaged in these activities and for the overall impact of such practices on the sustainability of a specific tourist destination. Today, environmental sustainability represents a significant competitive advantage for businesses and tourist destinations, especially considering the considerable environmental impact of the traditional hotel business model.

Recent scientific studies have analyzed how legal and regulatory constraints, on one hand, and pressure from various corporate stakeholders regarding environmental issues, on the other, are influencing business models and practices adopted by hospitality companies to minimize the environmental impact of their economic activities. Furthermore, given that there is a clientele willing to pay a “premium price” to companies demonstrating high ecological sensitivity and adopting “green” eco-sustainable management models, many operators are developing specific strategies. These strategies aim to enhance the environmental awareness of management, staff, and key suppliers while maximizing the return on investments in efficiency and environmental sustainability.

According to the main findings of this research field, the costs incurred for adopting optimal environmental management practices (EMPs – Environmental Management Practices) should not be seen merely as operating expenses. Instead, they can be considered investments that positively impact both the company itself and the tourist destination as a whole.

Indeed, there is a transformation in the relationship between hotel operators and their clientele, who are increasingly concerned about social and environmental issues, services, events, activities, and immersive experiences that a hotel and a tourist destination can offer.

At the individual company level, an environmental orientation—if properly developed and embedded in an organizational structure capable of sharing its underlying philosophy and objectives—becomes an additional economic resource. This allows the company to develop specific market strategies based on the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources. Businesses that can implement such strategies and possess the economic, financial, and operational capacity to do so can establish a strong, sustainable competitive advantage through improved customer satisfaction. The positive dynamics induced by increased customer satisfaction, in turn, enhance the company's market and financial performance.

Additionally, businesses must strategically and managerially structure their "Sustainability Reporting" and, more generally, "non-financial reporting," which is increasingly recognized as a driver of economic value. Companies are partially redefining their relationships with key stakeholders and aligning ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) reporting models with the informational needs of external audiences.

At the territorial production district level, due to the emulative behavior of economic agents and the adoption of competitors' best environmental practices, investments in eco-sustainable and low-impact practices can enhance the overall value of a tourist destination. This is achieved through the protection of natural resources and the enhancement of the local territory.

1.2 Conceptual framework and Methodology

The conceptual framework underpinning this study is the Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Natural-Resource-Based View (NRBV), a theoretical framework that allows for the analysis of the causal relationship between resources, growth, and business performance.

The study aims to test a series of hypotheses according to the conceptual model illustrated in Figure 1. The model seeks to capture the effects of drivers and outcomes in terms of the organization's overall performance, resulting from the implementation of business practices designed to develop processes, procedures, and operational routines focused on environmental sustainability.

The resources available to the company, along with its capabilities and competencies, act as drivers for the development and implementation of environmental strategies (EMPs). Additionally, factors such as capabilities, geographic location, and brand positioning serve as moderators of the relationship between environmental strategy and expected performance outcomes, which are measured based on financial, quantitative, and non-financial qualitative indicators.

The research methodology was developed according to the following steps:

- Step 1 – Literature review on the topic of sustainable policies (EMPs), with a particular focus on the tourism and hospitality sector;
- Step 2 – Development of hypotheses and research questions through discussions with a focus group of seven hotel entrepreneurs who have heavily invested in sustainable practices over the past ten years;
- Step 3 – Data collection and database integration through the analysis of financial statements and online ratings;
- Step 4 – Correlation analysis and testing of causal relationships between explanatory variables and dependent variables (multivariate regressions);
- Step 5 – Analysis and discussion of the results obtained, positioning them within the framework of previous theoretical and empirical research.

The study is currently in **Phase 3**. Unfortunately, we encountered several issues as far as empirical analysis is concerned, since we are struggling in collecting field raw data. After administering the structured questionnaire we designed to the members of **Chamber of Commerce/Hotel Association**, we observed a very low response rate. For this reason, we have shifted towards a different methodological approach to overcome this challenge.

So far, we have selected a sample of 320 hospitality establishments that hold a recognized environmental certification, indicating at least some sensitivity towards environmental practices.

Due to the lack of returned questionnaires, we had to revise our research strategy and turn to other innovative lines of inquiry that aim to operationalize certain input variables using AI tools and machine learning techniques, coupled with NLP solutions. In fact, we need to infer from publicly available data the proxies that will serve as inputs in our estimation model, particularly for dimensions such as ESG activities and organizational and relational capabilities, which are key components of the business models of the companies in our sample. We believe that if we manage to establishing a more representative and neutral empirical ground data, our results could better interpret company initiatives toward social responsibility, thus increasing the explanatory power of the relationship between sustainability and performance under investigation.

ESG and EMP are normally assessed by rating agencies using self-reporting company filings, with which companies can often portray themselves in an artificially positive light. Recent research has highlighted that these reports may be somehow biased and lead to

subjective and inconsistent analysis between different ESG rating organizations, despite them seeking to measure the same thing (Kotsanonis et al., 2019). Having more consistent and accurate ESG evaluation is important for our research. Furthermore, self-reporting allows companies with more resources to portray themselves better. This is why there is a significant positive correlation between a company's size, available resources, and ESG score (Drempetic et al., 2019).

These issues ultimately defeat the purpose of ESG by failing to motivate companies toward sustainable practices. From a research standpoint this raises the need for a more holistic and systemized approach to ESG evaluation that can more precisely measure a company's social responsibility.

By analyzing existing ESG-related research, we have identified two main large categories of studies.

Some papers aim to correlate ESG performance with financial performance and see if a company's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) can be used to predict future stock performance (Jain et al., 2019).

Other papers propose new data-driven methods for enhancing and automating ESG rating measurement to avoid existing fallacies/inefficiencies (Hisano et al., 2020; Krappel et al., 2021; Liao et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2018; Shahi et al., 2011; Sokolov et al., 2021; Venturelli et al., 2017; Wicher et al., 2019, Garcia et al 2020, Patel et al.2023). We decided to explore the applicability of this latter category for our study.

Given that many companies release annual sustainability reports, a growing body of research has leveraged this content for empirical analysis. A common approach involves applying text mining techniques to extract ESG-related themes and patterns from the reports. To structure this unstructured data, researchers have developed classification models capable of assigning sentences or paragraphs to specific ESG subdimensions (Liao et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2018). These models have also been employed to assess the completeness of sustainability disclosures (Shahi et al., 2011), acknowledging that firms may selectively omit information on negative ESG performance. Together, these tools support the automated scoring of ESG performance using public filings, offering a scalable solution for evaluating firms that lack standardized ESG ratings. And this is the typical situation of the companies of our sample.

Research has highlighted how relying exclusively on self-reported sustainability filings may present notable limitations, particularly due to the potential omission of unfavorable information and the lag in reporting more recent developments. In response, researchers have explored a range of alternative approaches to supplement or enhance ESG assessment, that are potentially interesting for our analysis. For instance, some studies have employed Fuzzy Expert Systems (FES) or the Fuzzy Analytic Network Process (FANP), integrating both quantitative indicators (e.g., Global Reporting Initiative metrics) and qualitative inputs derived from surveys and interviews (Venturelli et al., 2017; Wicher et al., 2019). Other scholars have turned to social media platforms, such as Twitter, leveraging Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to classify posts according to ESG themes and sentiment (Sokolov et al., 2021). Additionally, some have utilized heterogeneous information networks that aggregate negative news from multiple sources, applying machine learning models to predict ESG performance (Hisano et al., 2020). Further, there is growing interest in the predictive potential of fundamental data—including firm-level profiles and financials—as proxies for ESG performance (Krappel et al., 2021). Collectively, these methods aim to provide a more balanced, real-time, and less biased perspective on corporate sustainability, complementing or enhancing the insights derived from self-reported disclosures. We believe that this line of research may be effectively applied to our study.

Our approach thus aims to develop a synthetic and systematic ESG rating framework that delivers a more balanced and representative assessment of a company's socially responsible practices. To achieve this, we want to design an algorithm that leverages social network data to quantitatively evaluate ESG performance. Unlike self-reported disclosures, which are often subject to bias and selective transparency, social network data reflects a diverse range of external perspectives on the social and environmental issues the public expects corporations to address. By capturing real-time public sentiment, this approach mitigates the limitations of self-reporting and enables firms to better align their strategies with stakeholder expectations. Moreover, a data-driven model of this kind can extend ESG coverage to companies that currently lack formal ratings, like the companies of our sample, thus promoting broader accessibility and accountability.

This method is designed to generate metrics that capture intangible assets, such as Organizational Capital and Relational Capital, as well as a firm's orientation toward Environmental Management Practices and other non-financial indicators—such as customer satisfaction and occupancy rates—that reflect broader non-financial performance dimensions. These are the key metrics we need to measure in order to test

the research questions outlined in Figure 1. To achieve this, instead of relying solely on self-reported corporate filings, we utilized social network data to comprehensively quantify ESG performance. Social network analysis and web scraping techniques are effective in identifying trends (Gloor et al., 2009). Popular platforms such as Booking, TripAdvisor, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Google News offer a wealth of data relevant to ESG dimensions. When appropriately combined, this data can provide a more balanced perspective on a company's ESG practices.

We developed a comprehensive list of ESG-relevant keywords, drawing from subcategories commonly used in existing ESG rating frameworks. This list guided the collection of publicly available company data from institutional websites, TripAdvisor, Booking, Twitter, and Google News. Once the data is gathered, cleaned, and organized, it will be analyzed using Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms to generate specific metrics that can operationalize the desired ESG dimensions based on observed data.

Keywords/Topics we intend to use for data collection:

Environmental	Environment, carbon, emission, climate, pollution, sustainability
Social	Social, community, discrimination, diversity, human rights, labour
Governance	Governance, compensation, corruption, ethical, fraud, justice, transparency

This procedure will help us obtain those variables that act as proxies of Capabilities, EMP and non-financial performance indicators used in our model depicted in figure 1.

Proxy for ORCs.

We begin by defining Organizational and Relational Capabilities (ORCs) (H2) to operationalize these concepts and clarify their meaning.

□ Organizational Capabilities (OC):

- Resource Availability: Availability of financial, human, and technological resources.
- Operational Efficiency: Efficiency of internal processes, such as the ability to streamline operations.
- Innovation Capacity: The company's ability to innovate and adapt (e.g., through R&D).

- Leadership and Governance: Quality of leadership, decision-making processes, and governance structures.

□ Relational Capabilities (RC):

- Customer Relationships: Strength and depth of relationships with customers (e.g., customer retention, satisfaction).
- Partnerships and Collaborations: The number and quality of strategic partnerships and alliances.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Engagement with various stakeholders, including investors, communities, and regulators.
- Reputation and Brand Strength: Public perception, trust, and the strength of the brand.

Since these are intangible, qualitative resources that are not directly observable, we will need to use proxy variables from the available data we are attempting to collect. In this way, we should be able to construct a COR (Organizational and Relational Capabilities) index based on observable variables and then use this index in our regression model, with ESG or financial performance as the dependent variable.

Data sources we are approaching to retrieve necessary information are:

- Financial statements (PDFs, from business registries, simplified versions)
- Official websites of hotels / hotel groups
- Social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram)
- Tourism platforms (Booking, TripAdvisor)

This is an example of the operationalized variables we intend to collect:

Area	Proxy Variable	Source	Type
Internal Organization	Average number of employees per room	Financial Statements (personnel cost) / Website	Quantitative
	Training expenditure per employee	Financial Statements (notes)	Quantitative
	Employee turnover rate (%)	Financial Statements (if available)	Quantitative
External Relations	Number of partnerships or affiliations (e.g., tourist consortia, local institutions, global brands)	Website	Categorical/Count
	Presence of certifications (ISO 9001, Ecolabel, etc.)	Website	Dummy/Count

Governance and Transparency	Participation in sustainability programs (e.g., Green Key, EMAS, GRI)	Website	Dummy
	Presence of public organizational chart or management info	Website	Dummy
Communication and Openness	Presence of sustainability report or values statement	Website	Dummy
	Number of website languages	Website	Count
	Active "careers" section on the website	Website	Dummy
	Percentage of reviews responded to on external platforms (proxy for interaction)	External platforms (optional)	% Responses

Since the data for these variables will come in different scales (e.g., financial resources, customer satisfaction ratings), we will standardize or normalize them to allow for their combination into a single index. After normalizing and weighting the variables, we will combine them to form our final COR index by multiplying each standardized variable by its corresponding weight and then summing the results.

Proxy for EMP

A similar approach will be used to measure the EMP of the companies in our sample, starting with observable variables, to define meaningful Environmental/Sustainability Management proxies

To operationalize EMP, our idea is to look for:

- Strategic choices in the green area
- Active management initiative
- Declared commitments (certifications, policies, reporting)
- Concrete actions (dedicated resources, investments)

Here is a summarized table of the possible variables we intend to use:

Area	Proxy Variable	Source	Type
Declared Environmental Policies	Presence of a "sustainability" section on the website	Website	Dummy (0/1)
	Published sustainability report	Website	Dummy
	Environmental references in values/ethics statement	Website	Dummy
Environmental Certifications	Holding green certifications (e.g., ISO 14001, Ecolabel, EMAS, Green Key, etc.)	Website / Portals	Dummy/Count

Energy and Waste Management	Descriptions of energy-saving practices (e.g., LED lights, photovoltaics, smart systems)	Website	Dummy
	Plastic or waste reduction policies (e.g., no bottled water, dispensers)	Website	Dummy
	Recycling / composting / circular economy practices	Website	Dummy
Customer and Stakeholder Engagement	Green practices promoted to guests (towels, sheets, environmental info in room)	Website	Dummy
	Environmental projects in partnership with local organizations or NGOs	Website / Press Releases	Dummy
Dedicated Resources	Environmental investments (if reported in the financial statements or among costs)	Financial Statements	Amount or Dummy
	Presence of a "sustainability manager" or dedicated team	Website	Dummy

In this way we expect to define a solid and observable proxy to measure environmental sustainability management practices (EMP), in the hotel sector, using only publicly available data (e.g., financial statements, websites).

These variables should enable us to test hypotheses H1, H2, H4, H5a of our model. To test Hypothesis H3 and H5b, we need to obtain some proxies for occupancy rate and customer satisfaction.

Proxy for Occupancy Rate.

As direct data on hotel occupancy is typically unavailable in public sources, we intend to estimate occupancy rate indirectly using financial data reported in annual statements. Specifically, we will compute an approximate number of room-nights sold by dividing total accommodation revenues by an estimate of the hotel's Average Daily Rate (ADR), where available. The occupancy rate will then be derived by dividing the estimated number of room-nights sold by the maximum room capacity over the reference period (i.e., total number of rooms × number of days).

This proxy is commonly used in applied hospitality research and allows us to construct a performance indicator that reflects the demand-side utilization of hotel infrastructure in a consistent manner across firms. Despite potential noise introduced by assumptions on ADR, the measure remains robust for comparative purposes, especially when triangulated with other performance indicators. This approach is consistent with prior research in hospitality management that uses financial statement data to estimate key operational metrics such as occupancy rate and RevPAR (Chen et al., 2011; Kang et al., 2008; Hesford & Potter, 2010).

Proxy for Customer Satisfaction.

To calculate a Customer Satisfaction Index, we want to combine social media data collected (ratings, sentiment, and review volume) with balance sheet data (personnel costs and sustainability investments). The idea is to assign weights to the key components of social media data: for instance, a first hypothesis is to average rating (50%), sentiment score (30%), and review volume (20%). Then, we will create a financial score based on personnel costs (60%) and sustainability investments (40%). These individual scores will be normalized and combined, with the social media score weighted, for instance, at 70% and the financial score at 30%. This composite index will provide a comprehensive measure of customer satisfaction, combining both customer perceptions from social media and operational investments reflected in financial data

Our approach is consistent with prior research that integrates both social media data and financial metrics to assess customer satisfaction and business performance. Studies such as Chua and Banerjee (2013) and Liu and Mattila (2017) highlight the importance of sentiment analysis from social media platforms in understanding customer perceptions, while also showing the relevance of financial indicators like personnel costs and investments in improving service quality. Similarly, Rust and Zahorik (1993) and Grewal et al. (2003) explore how financial metrics, such as compensation and operational investments, influence customer satisfaction. By combining sentiment analysis, review volume, and financial data, our methodology aligns with this existing literature, offering a comprehensive approach to measuring customer satisfaction through both customer perceptions and business performance indicators.

By combining both social media data (ratings, sentiment, review volume) and balance sheet data (personnel costs, sustainability investments), we can build a reliable proxy for customer satisfaction. This proxy will allow us to assess a hotel's performance in terms of customer experience and will then be used in our models to connect it to financial and sustainability outcomes.

2. The model

2.1 Research model

In the context of this research contribution, the proposed model is used to analyze the following key topics:

- The relationship between investments in environmental practices and overall business performance;
- The effects of the availability of specific business resources (physical, financial, and organizational capabilities) on the effective and efficient implementation of eco-sustainable management practices;
- The logical and causal constructs linking the development of eco-sustainable environmental strategies to the creation of a sustainable competitive advantage (SCA), which, in turn, enables a company to achieve superior performance compared to its competitors;
- The direct or mediated relationship between the adoption of ESG reporting tools and corporate performance, both financial and non-financial.

Fig. 1 The Conceptual model

2.2 Implications for companies

The contribution of this research project from a managerial perspective is particularly significant, as the results help to:

1. Improve understanding of the link between environmentally oriented business processes and overall company performance;
2. Highlight the increasing awareness among customers, investors, and companies regarding environmental and overall sustainability issues in the tourism sector;

3. Demonstrate the effects of effective integrated ESG communication on business performance, as well as the role of such reporting practices as potential levers for differentiation from competitors;
4. Mitigate challenges related to external financing of intangible investments by broadening the range of possible funding options and reducing the cost of debt.

From a theoretical and research standpoint, the implications are equally relevant. In line with the findings of previous scientific, empirical, and theoretical research, the expected results emphasize the need to further explore the causal links and mechanisms between investments in environmental practices, the achievement of a sustainable competitive advantage, and business performance.

Beyond empirical testing aimed at analyzing current behaviors and evolving trends, the study underlines the importance of further theoretical investigation to identify specific metrics and indicators capable of serving as efficient proxies for measuring the operational profitability of such investments.

Finally, the study provides a starting point for deeper analysis of issues related to the structure and quality of corporate external disclosure. Given the growing trend to finance projects and activities with strong ESG components more readily, balanced financial and non-financial reporting—even in the simplified form proposed by Integrated Reporting—can be valuable, if not essential, in offering stakeholders a holistic view of the multiple dimensions of business performance. It also allows for better visibility and measurement of the outcomes generated by environmental sustainability decisions, ultimately leading to a more effective representation of investment choices and an expansion of external financing opportunities.

3. Conclusion

The challenges encountered during the research have slowed down the process, but they also provided an opportunity to identify new and more innovative methodological approaches, which will certainly add greater value to the results of the investigation for both businesses and the sector as a whole.